

Barrier Films based on EVOH and Graphene Oxide

Hey Min Kim^a, and Heon Sang Lee^{a*}

^aDepartment of Chemical Engineering, Dong-A University,
840, Hadan-dong, Saha-gu, Busan, 604-714 Korea

E-mail : heonlee@dau.ac.kr

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1. Introduction

Graphene, the 2D lattice of sp²-bonded carbon atoms from which graphite, carbon nanotubes, and fullerenes are derived, has emerged in recent years as a novel and important class of materials on its own merit. Graphene has exceptional physical, chemical, electrical and mechanical properties.[1-4] Another benefit from graphene is gas impermeable atomic membrane.[5]

Ethylene vinyl alcohol (EVOH) shows good thermal stability, high chemical resistance and gas been used as a food packaging material due to its excellent gas barrier properties and harmlessness toward health.[6]

In this work, we investigated the properties of GO/EVOH nanocomposites.

2. Experimental Section

2.1. Preparation of EVOH/GO composite film

GO was prepared from purified conventional flake graphite by modified Hummers method.

EVOH/GO nanocomposites were synthesized by solvent mixing method of EVOH in a colloidal solution of GO. EVOH/GO nanocomposites (0.1wt%) were as follows : EVOH(3g) was dissolved in distilled water and isopropyl alcohol (IPA) (weight ratio water/IPA = 1). A colloidal solution(6mL) of GO(3mg) was added to the EVOH solution and stirring for 24hr. Each EVOH/GO

hybrid solution was cast onto PET film and then dried for 1hr. The films were dried again in a vacuum oven for 4hr. A series of EVOH/GO nanocomposites films with different GO loadings were similarly prepared.

2.2. Characterization

Light transmittance of nanocomposites was measured with UV-vis at 550nm. Gas barrier of nanocomposites was measured with Illinois Instrument Model 8001. The differential scanning calorimetry(DSC) pettarn of samples were measured with DSC at a heating rate of 10°C/min. XRD experiments were performed directly on the hybrid samples with Cu irradiation at the scanning rate of 0.02/s in the 2 range of 2–40.

3. Result and Discussion

XRD indicated that GO was nearly exfoliated. (Fig.1.). Light transmittance at 550nm is 95.8% for the EVOH/GO composite film containing 0.1wt.% GO and 84.8% for the film containing 0.3wt.% (Fig.3.). The oxygen transmission rate (O₂TR) and water vapor transmission (WVTR) of EVOH/GO (0.3wt.%) composite reduces to 67% and 98% of that EVOH coated PET film. (Fig.4.).

4. Conclusion

GO is exfoliated in EVOH/GO composite. The O₂TR and WVTR of EVOH/GO (0.3wt.%) composite coated PET film is lower than that of pure PET film. The barrier property of EVOH film is improved when it is contained GO. EVOH/GO films are promising for the development of transparent high gas barrier film.

Fig.1. The XRD pattern of EVOH/GO nanocomposites.

Fig.2. DSC pattern of EVOH/GO composites.

Fig.3. Light transmittance of EVOH/GO film at 550nm.

Table 1. The oxygen permeability and water permeability of EVOH/GO film.

GO [wt.%]	P _{Oxygen} /P _{PET}	P _{Water} /P _{PET}
0	0.0198	7.0220e-4
0.15	0.0128	7.0391e-4
0.3	0.0124	6.9172e-4

5. References

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